

SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

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Abstract: One of the sources of financial support for small business entities is credit lines opened at the expense of funds allocated by international financial organizations and foreign banks. Structural changes in the economy of our republic require large investments. This article provides information on improving the management system of financial resources of small businesses and private enterprises.

Key words: small business, entrepreneurship, financial management, account, tax, income.

Small business entities operating under the laws of the market economy should have a clear idea of their current and future strategy, because the market does not forgive mistakes and thoughtless actions in the organization and planning of production. Any sensible person who wants to go on a long trip will definitely make a plan in advance - think about where to go and how to get there. The longer the event lasts, the more detailed the plan should be.

In the same way, before starting any activity, the manager of a small business must think about how to start it, what will be achieved as a result of this business activity, and how it can be implemented. If they want the business to be stable, they should have a long-term plan. For example, when the company "Kids at large" located in the state of Massachusetts (USA) was founded, the main goal of its strategic plan was to find "its own customer" in the market. Considering that 1 in 4 children in the US is overweight (obese), they set themselves the goal of producing clothing for children aged 4-14.

The ad showed good results because parents of overweight (obese) children had a hard time finding clothes. Kids at Large's strategy was to sell statewide through a mail-order program, instead of using traditional wholesale and retail chains. As a result of a well-designed business strategy, this company managed to receive 130,000 mail orders at a given time. The essence of the concept of strategic planning is that it is designed for the future, takes into account the high level of uncertainty in the development of the economy, is oriented towards the achievement of high-quality goals, and requires many options for approaching management. It presupposes a gap between the set goals and the achieved results. The main difference between strategic planning and long-term planning is that it is not possible to use development trends established in the past in strategic development. Here, a special place is devoted to the analysis and evaluation of all marketing risks and opportunities. In small business, economic-mathematical methods and models are widely used in strategic planning. The firm's strategy is a general action plan, with the help of which the firm strives to achieve its goals (algorithm of achieving goals).[3]

Small business strategy consists of detailing the main part of the company's strategy, summing up the quantitative and qualitative indicators and directions of its activity in the market, and the principle decisions that direct the company's strategy to specific measures of marketing that can be implemented more fully. A strategic plan is a set of operations, from the point of view of the head of the company, their implementation leads to the implementation of

his strategy. Tactics are developed for a short-term period (for example: a year, a quarter, a month) and, if necessary, are adjusted in order to solve the strategic tasks of the business. Creating an effective strategic plan requires the following step-by-step implementation: clearly defining the purpose of the company; analysis of business conditions, including the state of competition in the market, distributors and product suppliers, and their financial situation; clearly envision business activity and the process of its integration into production; consider external threats and strengths, internal opportunities and vulnerabilities, and competitive advantages.

Examination of risks and advantages, internal opportunities and subtleties is called SWOT analysis and is used in small/large business planning. The purpose, tasks, strategy, implementation and control of small business enterprise determine the amount of profit from this business. This should be considered and planned in advance. The relationship between the purpose, tasks, strategy and control of a small business enterprise with the amount of profit. A clear definition of the goal in planning is the guarantee of the success of a small business. It is known that goals are always implemented based on certain limitations.

They can be internal and external restrictions of a small business enterprise. External restrictions can include legal norms, inflation, competitors, changes in economic priorities, changes in incomes of the population, financial condition of debtors, etc. Internal constraints include the small business enterprise's cost level, production capacity, marketing and management status, various levels of inconsistencies, etc. Therefore, in the process of developing the mission, goals and tasks of a small business enterprise, it is necessary to evaluate a large number of factors affecting its activity.

In such cases, there are good reasons to consider the strategy of reducing employees in order to maintain and improve the level of production efficiency, as well as to increase the financial security of the company. This business management strategy has the following subtypes:

Termination. It is used only when the company has no possibility to exist. This is considered a business closure plan. **Immediate income.** The strategies of this subtype are used to maximize profit in minimum time. Usually it is used by companies that do not see their further development and want to leave the market. At the same time, they want to get the maximum possible profit in this process. To do this, they begin to reduce workers, stop providing goods and services, and reduce other costs that do not affect profits.

Partial closure. It is used in cases where the company wants to get rid of the non-commercial sector of its business or get additional funds that can be invested in successful production. **Reduce costs.** Such a business development strategy is used by companies that want to increase labor productivity and production efficiency. Ways to reduce costs are being sought for this. This can be achieved both by automating the production process and by reducing "extra" employees.

Such a development plan is divided into two subtypes:

Regulation of supply. This means strengthening control over suppliers of materials for production. In addition, it is possible to open their own branches or subsidiaries, which partially or fully fulfill the role of suppliers of raw materials. If one or two suppliers have the right raw materials, they can start setting their own conditions, which will be against the company's goals and will be unprofitable for it. In this case, it is better to start mining on your own and not continue.

Development of trade network. It often happens that sales points do not meet the level required for large sales and cannot satisfy all requirements in terms of quantity and quality. The purpose of this type of business strategy is to start selling goods independently as needed, as well as to improve the quality of current outlets. In this case, this is an excellent plan for the development of the company. Indicators of financial activity of small businesses and entrepreneurial entities. Basic financial documents of small business and entrepreneurial entities.[1]

Balance. Analysis of financial activities of small businesses and business entities. Types of financial analysis and methods of conducting them. The essence, purpose and main indicators of financial planning in small business and entrepreneurship. Sources of financing for small business and entrepreneurship. Forms of providing credit to small business entities. Types of loans. Other sources of financing of small business entities and their effective use. Development and financial support of small business is one of the important directions of the economic reforms implemented in our country, ensuring its development and increasing its weight in the national economy has risen to the level of state policy.

In their development, it is necessary to achieve the level of effective use of modern techniques and technologies of these subjects at the level of today's demand. "For this, it is necessary to constantly discover new sources of their development, both at the expense of attracting foreign investments, and at the expense of domestic sources and bank loans."

The main goal of this policy is not only to ensure quantitative growth of small business entities, but also to increase their efficiency. In these processes, lending them on a preferential basis is the most important link. At the center of lending to small business entities is the relationship of commercial banks based on mutually beneficial cooperation with them. Basing these relations on the basis of long-term processes allows the formation of a credit system for small business investment projects. Today, as part of the state support system for small business and private entrepreneurship, small business representatives have the following opportunities to use preferential loans for the organization, development and expansion of their activities. Targeted loans for the creation of new jobs at the expense of the State Fund for Employment Assistance to legal entities included in the regional and target programs of population employment in agreement with the banks providing services in the sum of 50,000 US dollars. is given in the amount up to the equivalent.

Microcrediting of small business entities for the purposes of expansion of production and development of activities at the expense of extra-budgetary funds is carried out on the basis of a preferential interest rate calculated by adding the bank margin. The preferential interest rate for these microloans is set in fixed percentages compared to the current refinancing rate of the Central Bank. Today, small business and private entrepreneurship make up 13% of the national economy, 14% of jobs and 58% of GDP are created in this sector. For comparison, in the Russian Federation this indicator is 13% and 14%, and in the European Union it is 18% and 20%. The share of small enterprises in Uzbekistan is 7-9 percent of the total number of enterprises, and their economic indicators are on average 26 percent. Today, the share of small and medium-sized businesses in the number of enterprises operating in our country is 14 percent, and small enterprises with the status of legal entities are 50 percent. It can be seen that the main share of entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan is small business. It should

be noted that the share of small businesses (micro, small, medium) in the EU gross domestic product is proportional to 60% on average.[5]

One of the main reasons for the significant slowdown in the development of small business at the level of foreign countries is the lack of financial resources, especially own funds, high interest rates on bank loans and the complexity of procedures, insufficient demand for products in the foreign market, and a stable economic situation. conditions. Considering that most of these factors depend on the external environment and are formed in accordance with the requirements of the world market, reducing the deficit of internal financial resources and increasing the efficiency of their use directly indicates the ineffectiveness of reengineering business processes and financial management methods. This situation requires paying special attention to the financial aspects of management in improving the efficiency of small business activities.

Effective, well-organized and high-quality financial management system ensures financial stability and development of small business. At the same time, in our country, the use of advanced management methods is being improved in the activities of small business entities, in particular, in the organization of financial management. These problems are manifested in the insufficient ability of small enterprises to fill the domestic market with local products, the low efficiency of production techniques and technologies, as well as difficulties in bringing products to the market and, as a result, the return of investments directed to this sector. The above circumstances do not allow small businesses to work effectively. The implementation of tasks to eliminate them and increase their effectiveness requires further improvement of financial management methods and processes. Among the above issues are the use of financial management methods in small business, their improvement, including the evaluation of the current status, effectiveness, and efficiency of financial management methods in the selected field of economic activity, and further improvement of the financial management system stability and development of author's proposals. Basically, increasing the share of small business in the national economy is one of the urgent tasks of today.

Our state pays special attention to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. In particular, the lack of funds of the Presidential Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" PQ 4947 , high interest rates and complexity of procedures for bank loans, insufficient demand for products in the foreign market and stable economic situation. conditions. Considering that most of these factors depend on the external environment and are formed in accordance with the requirements of the world market, reducing the deficit of internal financial resources and increasing the efficiency of their use directly indicates the ineffectiveness of reengineering business processes and financial management methods. This situation requires paying special attention to the financial aspects of management in improving the efficiency of small business activities.

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Development of stability and author's offers Basically, increasing the share of small business in the national economy is one of the urgent tasks of today. Our state pays special attention to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. In particular, the improvement of the Presidential Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" No. 4947, small business and private entrepreneurship As a result of the implementation of complex measures to encourage rapid development and support them in all aspects, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country's gross domestic product is increasing year by year and is more than 53.3 percent. In recent years, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship has been increasing in all sectors of the economy. The achievement of independence of Uzbekistan created wide opportunities for the realization of the centuries-old dreams of the Uzbek people and the rise of our country, the comprehensive development of our economy, the expansion and improvement of its structure, the increase of the people's well-being and the free and prosperous life of the population. It is known that in the former USSR, under the influence of the all Union division of labor, each economic region and each allied republic specialized in a certain complex. The economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan was specialized in the cotton complex, and cotton production, processing and service industries were developed here. Therefore, as a result of the one-sided development of the republic's economy, as a result of the failure of cooperative relations between the republics of the former union, the state of the economy has sharply deteriorated, that is, the production of products in the industrial and other sectors of the economy has sharply decreased, there is a shortage of products of primary necessity. began to be felt and the standard of living of the population began to decrease.[2]

Naturally, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, which has a strong economic potential, has almost all the elements of the Mendeleev table in large quantities underground, has very favorable natural and climatic conditions, developed means of communication and talented personnel it was impossible to agree to such a situation. Declaring 2011 as the "year of small business private entrepreneurship" in our country is the result of the fact that our state considers the rapid development of small business, which is the most effective form of economic management, as a priority task and has been giving it various benefits.

Among the benefits given, tax benefits occupy a special place. This is confirmed by the opinion of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, who said, "It is planned to significantly reduce the tax burden, first of all, for small business and private entrepreneurship. The single tax payment rate for them has been reduced from 6% to 5%." It is known that each science has its own subject, that is, its own object of study. For example,

the subject of the subject "Taxes and taxation" is the economic nature of taxes and compulsory payments equivalent to them, their role in the formation of state budget revenues, the independent tax policy and tax system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, benefits by types of taxes and taxes. will serve to study the mechanism of calculation and payment to the budget. The subject of the subject "Taxation of small business and private entrepreneurship" is the same as the subject of the subject "Taxes and taxation", only on the example of small business and private entrepreneurship. The tax mechanism means the application of the tax system to the tax practice. The tax mechanism includes the study of monetary transactions or tax practice and serves to study the totality of all tax elements that make up taxes related to taxation.[4]

Here, money transactions are carried out between taxpayers, that is, small businesses and private entrepreneurs, and the state (tax collectors). The importance of small business development is the ability to create new jobs at a low cost, the ability to occupy market segments that cannot be penetrated by large businesses, especially in the service sector and the development of small local resource bases. shows incomparability. For this reason, the issue of rapid development of small business is closely connected with the issues of localization of production, development of the service sector, as well as increasing the country's export potential. One of the sources of financial support for small business entities is credit lines opened at the expense of funds allocated by international financial organizations and foreign banks.

CONCLUSION:

Structural changes in the economy of our republic require large investments. Currently, foreign credit lines are of great importance in the development of the economy of Uzbekistan, in the financing of projects implemented in small business enterprises. Loans at the expense of foreign credit lines are granted to small business entities for investment projects intended for export and production of import-substituting products, agricultural products and other raw material resources, as well as production of other daily consumer goods. Because in order to produce exportable products, small business enterprises need to introduce the latest techniques and technologies in production.

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